

PREPARATION OF SULFONATED MAGNETIC CHITOSAN FOR METHYLENE BLUE ADSORPTION

Haya Fathana, Rahmi¹, Susilawati¹, Ismaturrahmi¹, Nilawati¹

¹Chemistry department, syiah kuala university, darussalam- banda aceh

¹rahmi@fmipa.unsyiah.ac.id

Abstract

Preparation of sulfonated magnetic chitosan had been conducted and applied for methylene blue adsorption. Sulfonated magnetic chitosan was prepared using Fe_3O_4 isolated from iron sand and sulfonating agent prepared from NaNO_2 and NaHSO_3 with various pH (5, 6 and 9). The obtained sulfonated magnetic chitosan was characterized by Transform Infrared (FT-IR), X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) and Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). FTIR results showed the presence of sulfonate and Fe-O groups in the sulfonated magnetic chitosan that indicated sulfonated magnetic chitosan successfully prepared. XRD patterns showed the crystallinity of chitosan decreased by addition of Fe_3O_4 and sulfonation agent. SEM results showed the structure of sulfonated magnetic chitosan has a rougher surface than the pure chitosan. Removal percentage of methylene blue from water by sulfonated magnetic chitosan was higher than pure chitosan. This indicated that the sulfonated magnetic chitosan can be used as an adsorbent of methylene blue.

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1. Introduction

Development of industry has increased rapidly which affects the increasing amount of waste from industrial wastewater. One of the most frequently found liquid wastes is textile dyes from textile product residues [1]. Textile dyes are generally made of compounds containing benzene groups such as methylene blue, rhodamine B, yellow methanol and tatrazine. However, the most common textile dyes in the textile industry is methylene blue [2].

Methylene blue is a toxic dye that is very harmful to the environment and human life. The presence of methylene blue in aqueous environments (even though in low concentration, 1 ppm) can affect the photosynthetic process of plants in the water that inhibits the sunlight. If the activity of the textile industry in each process produces methylene blue waste and pollutes the aquatic environment it can be ascertained that the aquatic environment becomes damaged [3].

One process that is very effective for removing methylene blue from the aquatic environment is the adsorption process using adsorbent [4]. Chitosan is one of the natural polymers that can be used as an adsorbent to remove methylene blue from wastewater. In order to improve the adsorption capacity of chitosan, some modifications have been conducted such as addition of functional groups into chitosan [5], and addition of Fe_3O_4 into chitosan that provides magnetic properties of chitosan where chitosan will be easily separate from solution [6]. In this work, chitosan was sulfonated by sulfonating agent which prepared from NaNO_2 and NaHSO_3 . Sulfonated chitosan was then added with Fe_3O_4 isolated from the iron sand of Aceh, Indonesia.

The obtained sulfonated magnetic chitosan was characterized by FTIR, XRD and SEM. The adsorption capacity of sulfonated magnetic chitosan was examined for methylene blue adsorption.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Chitosan was purchased from Tokyo Chemical Industry Co., Ltd. Japan (obtained from shrimp shell where deacetylation degree was 75.0-85.0%). Iron sand was collected from Syiah Kuala, Aceh, Indonesia.

2.2. Isolation of Fe_3O_4 from iron sand

Fe_3O_4 has been isolated from iron sand using the co-precipitation method. Iron sand was added to 100 mL of HCl 12.07 M and stirred using a magnetic stirrer for 30 min at 70 °C. Then the undissolved compounds were filtered. After filtration, ammonia was added to the solution at 70 °C until pH 6 was reached. The obtained precipitate was rinsed repeatedly using distilled water until neutral pH was reached and then dried at 70°C for 10 hours [7].

2.3. Preparation sulfonation agent

$NaNO_2$ solution was poured into $NaHSO_3$ solution with a ratio of 1: 4.25 at 90°C and stirred using a magnetic stirrer for 1.5 hours [8].

2.4. Preparation of sulfonated magnetized chitosan

Chitosan 0.35 g was immersed in sulfonation agent solution at different pH (5, 6, and 9) for 24 hours. Then it was rinsed with distilled water until neutral pH was reached and dried at 40°C for 7 hours. The sulfonated chitosan was dissolved with 20 mL of acetic acid 2% and stirred using a magnetic stirrer for 2 hours. 0.5 g of Fe_3O_4 isolated from iron sand of Syiah Kuala was added to the sulfonated chitosan solution and stirred for 1 hour. The mixture was added into a syringe and dropped into the solution of NaOH 3M. The obtained beads were rinsed with distilled water until pH 7 was reached and dried at 40°C.

2.5. Characterization

The obtained Fe_3O_4 , pure chitosan and sulfonated magnetic chitosan were characterized by FTIR, SEM, and XRD analysis.

2.6. Adsorption studies

0.1 g of adsorbent was added to 10 mL of methylene blue solution 30 ppm and shaken for 25 minutes. Then the adsorbent was separated from the solution using a permanent magnet. The concentration of methylene blue remained in the solution was determined using UV-Vis spectrophotometer at 655 nm. Methylene blue adsorption capacity (Q_e , mg/g) and removal percentage (Removal, %) were calculated using the following equations:

$$Q_e = \frac{(C_0 - C_t)V}{m} \quad (1)$$

$$Removal = \frac{C_0 - C_t}{C_0} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Where C_0 (mg/g) and C_i (mg/L) are the initial and final concentration of methylene blue, respectively. V (L) is the volume of methylene blue solution and m (g) is the mass of the adsorbent.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization

In order to study the functional groups contained in chitosan and sulfonated magnetic chitosan beads, FTIR analysis was performed. The results were shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. FTIR spectra of chitosan (a) and sulfonated magnetic chitosan beads (b)

Figure 1a showed FTIR spectrum of chitosan. Absorption bands at wavenumber 3427 and 1633 cm^{-2} associated with O-H and N-H vibrations, respectively. These bands are typical bands of chitosan. Figure 1b was FTIR spectrum of sulfonated magnetic chitosan beads. Compared with FTIR spectrum of chitosan, FTIR spectrum of sulfonated magnetic chitosan beads exhibited some differences. Absorption band of O-H vibration at wave number 3427 cm^{-1} in chitosan spectrum shifted to lower wavenumber 3408 cm^{-1} in sulfonated magnetic chitosan beads. It was due to the presence of hydrogen bond. Absorption band at wavenumber 898 cm^{-1} correlated to the presence of C-O-S vibration that indicated chitosan was successfully sulfonated. In addition, absorption band at wavenumber 582 cm^{-1} showed typical band of Fe-O which indicated Fe_3O_4 was successfully inserted in the chitosan.

Figure 2. SEM images of chitosan bead

Figure 3. SEM images of sulfonated magnetic chitosan bead

SEM analysis was conducted to study the morphology of adsorbents. Figure 2 showed SEM images of chitosan bead and Figure 3 showed SEM image of sulfonated magnetic chitosan bead. Chitosan bead exhibited the smoother surface than sulfonated magnetic chitosan bead. These results indicated the presence of filler (Fe_3O_4) which was distributed in the sulfonated chitosan. Sulfonated magnetic chitosan bead showed a smaller particle size than chitosan bead.

Figure 4. XRD patterns of chitosan (a) and sulfonated magnetic chitosan beads (b)

In order to study crystallinity of the adsorbents, XRD analysis was performed. The results were shown in Figure 4. Figure 4a and 4b showed XRD patterns of chitosan and sulfonated magnetic chitosan beads, respectively. XRD pattern of chitosan showed a sharp peak at $2\theta = 19.5^\circ$, where this pattern is typical for chitosan [9]. The sulfonation and addition of Fe_3O_4 in chitosan reduced the crystallinity of chitosan and the typical peak of chitosan was not found in XRD pattern of sulfonated magnetic chitosan bead. Low intensity at $2\theta = 35.42^\circ$ in XRD pattern of

sulfonated magnetic chitosan bead showed typical peak of Fe_3O_4 which indicated Fe_3O_4 was successfully inserted in the preparation of sulfonated magnetic chitosan bead. The decrease in intensity at $2\theta = 19.5^\circ$ indicated the structure of chitosan became amorphous. This amorphous structure is favorable for adsorption process, where adsorption capacity of sulfonated magnetic chitosan bead was higher than chitosan as shown in Figure 5.

3.2. Adsorption study

Figure 5 showed the adsorption capacity and removal percentage of methylene blue by sulfonated magnetic chitosan beads at different pH of sulfonation process.

Figure 5. Effect of sulfonation pH of chitosan on adsorption capacity and removal percentage of sulfonated magnetic chitosan beads

Based on Figure 5, the highest adsorption capacity was found at sulfonation pH 5. The adsorption capacity was 2.037 mg/g and the removal percentage was 67.9%. These results are in accordance with the theoretical that in the condition of the acid the amine group in chitosan will be protonated and the oxygen atom in the hydroxy group becomes more electronegative. The reaction that occurs in sulfonation of chitosan is an electrophilic substitution reaction in which electropositive sulfur atoms will be attacked by free electron pairs on oxygen atoms [10]. In addition, the addition of Fe_3O_4 affected the increase in adsorption capacity, because the oxygen contained in Fe_3O_4 also contributed to the adsorption of methylene blue. These results showed sulfonation and addition of Fe_3O_4 increased adsorption capacity of chitosan and the adsorbent could be easily separated from the solution. The pictures of methylene blue before and after adsorption process were shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Methylene blue before (a) and after (b) adsorption by sulfonated magnetic chitosan beads

4. Conclusions

Sulfonation of chitosan and addition of Fe_3O_4 decreased crystallinity of chitosan. Adsorption capacity and removal percentage of chitosan in methylene blue adsorption process increased after modification (67.9%). The optimum condition of chitosan sulfonation was found at pH 5.

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